

ENHANCING USER EXPERIENCE IN ELEVATOR SERVICE – A FIELD STUDY

Dr.Sai Ganesh

Professor, School of Commerce and Management Studies, Dayananda Sagar University

Dr.Amulya Prasad Panda

Adjunct Professor, School of Commerce and Management Studies

Dayananda Sagar University

Dr.Shweta Tewari

Associate Professor, School of Commerce and Management Studies

Dayananda Sagar University

Abstract

Elevator is a crucial aspect of vertical transportation in various settings such as commercial buildings, residential complexes, and public facilities. Rapid urbanization, commercial activity, infrastructural development are the major factors that are fuelling the market growth for the India elevator market. Thanks to the advanced manufacturing technology, the gaps in product cost and quality are narrowing down among the competitors in the elevator industry. Customer satisfaction has become a robust measure for businesses looking to increase their competitiveness. A study was taken up to understand users' preferences and their potential pain points, analyse the data in order to provide actionable insights for various stakeholders such as the elevator companies, owners and the elevator service providers in order to enhance the overall user experience.

Keywords: *Elevator, User Experience, Maintenance, Customer Survey, Elevator Safety*

1.0 Introduction

The elevator market in India is undergoing a transformative phase, marked by significant growth driven by rapid urbanization, population expansion, and the rise of the middle class. Key metropolitan areas such as Delhi-NCR, Mumbai, and Bangalore are witnessing a surge in demand for elevators and escalators, fuelled by the construction of tall buildings, commercial complexes, and innovative infrastructure projects.

Traditionally, businesses competed more and more on the basis of product performance, quality, and cost (Porter Michale E 1985; Jagdev,1998). However, with the gaps in the product cost and quality, the focus is shifting towards building strong relationships with customers with superior customer service. Consumers today engage with businesses through a multitude of touchpoints across various media and platforms, and their interactions are more social in character. Due to these developments, businesses must now connect several departments and even outside partners in order to create and provide satisfying client experiences (Catherine *et al.* 2016). Nguyenvan *et al.* (2020) underscored how providing excellent customer service helped to forge lasting bonds with clients and lessen their propensity towards the rival businesses.

Customer satisfaction is a psychological state that results from comparing customers' psychological expectations and feelings after making a purchase (Barsky, 1992). Enhanced

products that meet real customer needs are required to raise customer satisfaction with the business's offerings. (Kordupleski, 1993). The Consumer Satisfaction Index (CSI) is a model that businesses have created by combining extensive consumer evaluations of their services and products with data analysis and model computation (Fornel, 1996). Xiang Haifei (2022) used a technique called “*multilevel grey relational analysis*” to create an elevator maintenance customer satisfaction assessment system incorporating the aspects of what customers’ desire from a product.

Elevator companies and/or service providers are vying for superior customer service using advanced technology, standardization and root-cause analysis of elevator breakdowns. Lai *et al.* (2017) conducted a study on the ways in which modern technology, specifically the Internet of Things (IoT), can help traditional manufacturing companies transition to a more service-oriented business model. Liu, H., & Wu, J. (2018) studied the optimum maintenance strategy of elevators, in terms of the number and interval of preventive maintenance, in order to minimize the failure rate of elevators. According to Alshehri *et al.* (2015), the lack of standards for maintenance and service activities results in poor performance of a system. Au-Yong *et al.* (2018) explored that vandalism is the main reason for the frequent breakdown of lifts, especially in low-cost residential housing. Vandalism is a significant issue in residential complexes (Laila, 2015).

2.0 Methodology: Customer Satisfaction Survey

Customer satisfaction survey can help the elevator service providers choose from among a long list of service attributes to focus their organization’s attention and resources more optimally. This case study delves into the intricacies of elevator user experience through a comprehensive survey conducted with 463 users drawn as from various walks of society in the city of Bengaluru, India.

3.0 Participants’ Profile

Table 1 reports the demography of the participants in the customer satisfaction survey. Majority of the respondents fall within a range of 18-35 years of age, with a fairly even gender distribution i.e. male: female = 57% : 43%. The occupation of the participants include students, office goers, home makers and others, such as temporary workers, visitors etc. The purpose of choosing a demography with a diverse range of occupations is to remove the bias of a certain section of the users.

Table 1
Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Gender	Male	Female		
	57%	43%		
Age	18-25	26-35	36-45	46 & Above
	28%	42%	22%	8%
Occupation of participants	Students	Office Workers	Home Maker	Others
	26%	49%	19%	6%
Frequency of usage	Daily	Occasionally	Rarely	
	73%	22%	5%	

As shown in Table 1, a significant portion (73%) of respondents use elevators daily, either in commercial settings and/or in official buildings and/or in high-rise residential complexes. The

category, missing in the survey, are the elevators used for industrial applications, such as in power plants, oil refineries, mining etc.

4.0 Customer Feedback

The survey captured the users' feedback on different aspects, such as: Cleanliness & Maintenance, Safety & Security and User Interface & Information. Each of these attributes have been discussed in detail in the following sections.

4.1: Cleanliness

The cleanliness of elevators refers to the state of hygiene and tidiness within elevator cabins or the elevator environment as a whole. It encompasses various aspects such as:

- **Sanitary Conditions:** Ensuring that the elevator interiors are free from dirt, dust, spills, and other forms of contamination. This includes regular cleaning of surfaces, floors, walls, and buttons.
- **Odour Control:** Maintaining a fresh and pleasant atmosphere inside the elevator by addressing any unpleasant odours promptly. Emptying trash bins inside elevators regularly to prevent accumulation of waste and foul smells.
- **Disinfection:** Especially important in public or shared spaces, regular disinfection of high-touch surfaces like buttons, handrails, and walls to minimize the risk of spreading germs and viruses.

Cleanliness in elevators is essential not only for aesthetic reasons but also for public health and safety, particularly in high-traffic areas where elevators are frequently used by many people. It contributes to a more comfortable and hygienic transportation experience for passengers. As shown in Table 2, 60% of the users were quite happy with the general cleanliness of the elevators. This is due to the higher standard of living in a city, compared to the some of the tier 2 or 3 cities.

Table 2
User Feedback

Parameters	Feedback		
	Satisfied	Neutral	Dissatisfied
Cleanliness & Maintenance	67%	26%	7%
Safety & Security	76%	6%	18%
User Interface & Information	77%	18%	5%

4.2: Safety & Security

While a majority (i.e. 76%) of the participants (Table 2) feel safe, a good 18% are concerned about their safety while using the elevators. Safety perceptions may vary depending on the type of building or facility. Elevators in newer or well-maintained buildings may be perceived as safer compared to older or poorly maintained structures. There have been occasional reports of elevator accidents or malfunctions in India, which can contribute to concerns about safety. Instances such as elevator breakdowns, getting stuck between floors, or doors malfunctioning may raise apprehensions among the public. India does have regulations and standards in place governing the installation, operation, and maintenance of elevators. However, enforcement of these regulations may vary, and there have been instances where

safety guidelines are not strictly adhered to. Regular maintenance and inspections are crucial for ensuring the safety of elevators. However, in some cases, maintenance schedules may not be followed diligently, leading to potential safety hazards. Besides customer dissatisfaction, elevator breakdowns can cause serious health and safety issue for its users (Park & Yang, 2010).

4.3 Ease of Usage

As shown in Table 2, the majority of the users, i.e. 77% are happy with the ease of use of the elevators. The general opinion regarding the ease of usage of elevators can vary based on several factors such as location, building type, technology level, and maintenance standards. Elevators in modern buildings equipped with user-friendly interfaces, clear signage, and advanced features tend to be easier to use compared to older elevators with outdated technology.

Elevators that are well-maintained are generally perceived as easier to use and more reliable. However, instances of elevators being out of service or experiencing frequent breakdowns due to inadequate maintenance can lead to frustration among users. Factors such as elevator size, speed, capacity, and accessibility features (such as Braille buttons and audible announcements) can influence the ease of usage, particularly for individuals with disabilities or mobility challenges.

Cultural norms and social etiquette can also influence the ease of usage of elevators. For example, crowded elevators may be perceived as less comfortable or convenient, particularly during peak hours. Providing clear instructions on how to use elevators and promoting awareness about elevator etiquette can enhance the ease of usage for all users. This includes educating individuals on proper elevator etiquette, such as allowing passengers to exit before entering and not overcrowding the elevator beyond its capacity.

5. Suggestions and Recommendations

Based on the analysis of the elevator feedback survey, the following recommendations are proposed to enhance the overall experience for users:

5.1 Prioritizing Maintenance and Inspection

Annual Maintenance Contract (AMC) is mandated by the State laws across India, which ensures regular maintenance schedules, typically once a month, ensuring smooth operation elevators minimizing downtime and disruptions. Maintenance is of two types, such as:

- a. Preventive maintenance: Periodic greasing, adjustments, and observations of all the elements of an elevator.
- b. Corrective maintenance: Repairs, Replacement of parts (callbacks)

The field study found out that, the public/commercial buildings, hardly have any issues in the renewal of AMCs year-on-year. However, there are delays in residential sectors, where the building maintenance is overseen by the associations of the residents. There is a need to create an awareness for a safe elevator.

The elevator service providers could work closely with building management teams to implement a comprehensive approach to elevator management. This may involve coordinating maintenance schedules, addressing security concerns, and ensuring a consistent and high standard of service across all elevators in a building. Additionally, they could explore and invest in modern elevator technologies that can enhance overall performance, efficiency, and user satisfaction. This may include adopting smart systems, predictive maintenance technologies, or energy-efficient solutions.

5.2 Optimizing Elevator Speed and Capacity:

Some respondents of the survey were concerned of crowding, especially during peak times, which could be alleviated with faster elevators by exploring technologies that can increase speed without compromising safety. Additionally the design and layout of elevators could be assessed to determine if there are opportunities to optimize space usage and reduce the likelihood of crowding. This could involve implementing more efficient entry and exit systems or exploring smart technologies to manage crowd flow.

5.3 Enhancing Safety Measures:

While majority of the respondent are reasonably happy with the safety of the elevators, there is still a scope to improved perception of safety with improved lighting, strategically placed emergency buttons, and increased surveillance to enhance security within elevator spaces. Additionally, clear and helpful signage or digital displays within the elevator could improve the perception of safety.

The service providers could consider implementing initiatives to educate users about elevator usage, safety features, and emergency procedures. Well-informed users are likely to feel more confident and secure during elevator use.

6.0 Conclusion

The examination of the user experience of elevators through a comprehensive survey and analysis offers valuable insights into key factors influencing satisfaction, safety. Maintenance emerged as a critical concern, underscoring the need for proactive servicing to enhance reliability. Recommendations to optimize elevator speed, capacity, and safety measures are pivotal for addressing user concerns and improving overall satisfaction. The study also emphasizes the importance of user interface enhancements and effective communication within elevator spaces. By embracing these recommendations, stakeholders in elevator management can create an environment that not only meets user expectations but also fosters a sense of security and efficiency in vertical transportation.

References

1. Abdul Mohit, M., Ibrahim, M., & Rashid, Y. R. (2010). Assessment of residential satisfaction in newly designed public low cost housing in Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia. *Practice, Habitat International*, 34, 18-27.
2. Alshehri, A., Motawa, I., & Ogunlana, S. (2015). The common problems facing the building maintenance departments. *International Journal of Innovation, Management and Technology*, 6(3), 234-237.
3. Au-Yong, C. P., Azmi, N. F., & Mahassan, N. A. (2018). Maintenance of lift systems affecting resident satisfaction in low-cost high-rise residential buildings. *Journal of Facilities Management*, 16(1), 17-25. doi: 10.1108/JFM-04-2017-0015
4. Barsky, J. D., & Labagh, R. (1992). A strategy for customer satisfaction. *Cornell Hotel and Restaurant Administration Quarterly*, 33(5), 32-40.
5. Jagdev, H. S., & Browne, J. (1998). The extended enterprise-a context for manufacturing. *Production Planning & Control*, 9(3), 216-229.
6. Kordupleski, R. E., Rust, R. T., & Zahorik, A. J. (1993). Why improving quality doesn't improve quality (or whatever happened to marketing? *California Management Review*, 35(3), 82-95.

7. Katherine N. Lemon and Peter C. Verhoef PC. (2016) Understanding Customer Experience Throughout the Customer Journey. *Journal of Marketing*. Volume 80, Issue 6
8. Liu, H., & Wu, J. (2018). Research on preventive maintenance strategy of elevator equipment. *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 6(01), 165.
9. Lai, C. T., Jackson, P. R., & Jiang, W. (2017). Shifting paradigm to service-dominant logic via Internet-of-Things with applications in the elevators industry. *Journal of Management Analytics*, 4(1), 35-54.
10. Laila, K. (2015). Suggested guidelines for integrating maintenance considerations into the life cycle of the building. *Journal of Construction*, 8(1), 1-10.
11. Mohite, Gajanan R et al (2018) : A Review Paper on Major & Minor Causes of Accidents in Elevators in Metro City, Jr for Research, Volume 04, Issue 10, ISSN:2395-7549
12. Nguyenvan DT, Pham VT, Tran MD, Pham, BD (2020). Impact of Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction and Switching Costs on Customer Loyalty. *Journal of Asian Finance & Business*. Vol. 7. No.8, p395-405.
13. Porter, Michale E (1985). *The Competitive Advantage: Creating & Sustaining Superior Performance*. NY: Free Press
14. Park, S. T., & Yang, B. S. (2010). An implementation of risk-based inspection for lift maintenance. *Journal of Mechanical Science and Technology*, 24(12), 2367-2376.
15. Robinson, N & Uma Raman N (2022). A study on health & safety measures provided by elevator industries in Chennai. *International Journal of Mechanical Engineering*, ISSN: 0974-5823, Vol. 7 No.4 April, 2022
16. Xiang Haifei (2022). The Influence of Elevator Maintenance Program on Customer Satisfaction Based on Multi-Level Grey Relational Analysis. *Academic Journal of Computing & Information Science*. Vol. 5, Issue 2: 17-23, ISSN 2616-5775.